
IMPORTANCE OF RELIGIOUS EDUCATION AND MOTIVATION IN STATE DEFENSE; A PERSPECTIVE OF ISLAMIC REPUBLIC OF PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The demand for a separate homeland by Muslims in the Subcontinent was an outcome of their intent and emotions, their cultural and political identity, whose origins were entrenched in the Islamic welfare state of Madina which was founded by Holy Prophet Mohammad (PBUH) and was further developed and strengthened by Khulafa-e-Rashideen. In this perspective, Pakistan movement was started on the basis of Islamic ideology. It was an obvious result of a long and terrible struggle for the Muslims of Subcontinent that Pakistan came into being as the first Islamic State, after the state of Madina, which emerged as an ideological state based on Islam.

Armed Forces of Pakistan being the Defense Forces of an Ideological Islamic State must inherit the legacy of spirit of Islam that needs to run through the very vein of every soldier. Keeping this background in view, this research article will elaborate the co-relation of Islam and existence of Islamic Republic of Pakistan by pointing out historical realities. The way by which Islam educates and motivates its followers for Jihad and State Defense will also be elaborated by referring Verses from Holy Quran. This research work will also elaborate that how religious motivational education and instructions are playing a role of multiplying force in strengthening this spirit and acting as a hub around which, all the elements of state defense of Pakistan are strongly knitted; and how this is constructing a belief system that is enhancing the potential of soldiers even to sacrifice their precious lives.

Keywords: Islamic Ideology, State Defense, Holy Quran, Religious Education, Pakistan.

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